

ENGLISH TRANSLATIONS OF THE HOLY QURAN: HISTORICAL TIMELINE

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***Abstract** The article discusses the historical timeline of English translations of the Holy Quran in the Western world with clear statistical analysis.*

***Key words:** Quran, translation methods, English translations, timeline, western approach.*

The Holy Qur'an, with its syntactically perfect text structure, semantically rich vocabulary essence with ageless in terms of use, easy-to-understand literary interpretation and having beautiful artistic style of expression and invariable grammatical structure, which is not present in most languages, has been attracting the attention of the world scientific community for more than 14 centuries. But, as in every era, not all world scientists who want to do research over the scientific truth of this holy Scripture within the framework of modern science know Classical Arabic (Fus'ha), the language through which the Holy Qur'an was revealed, so that they often address to the Holy Qur'an in English language, which has become the international scientific language of today.¹

When the talk comes on the information about the first acquaintance of the English-speaking societies with the Holy Qur'an, it is necessary to note that such information is not a simple process that is simply overlooked as a historical reality, because that was the times, how western aggressive Islamophobia against Islam has arisen and those periods are telling us role purposes of today's the religious-political discord, opposition and bloody conflict between Muslims and Western nations. That

¹ Alsaleh Brakhw, A. A. M., & Shaik Ismail, S. F. (2014). The Importation of the Holy Quran into English: Governing Factors in the Translating Process. Arab World English Journal.

is why the history of these periods should be studied with special attention. For this purpose, in this part of our research, we decided to cover the history of the translation of the Holy Qur'an into English on the basis of historical documents and information obtained from various foreign electronic archives of source studies, international museums and libraries, which we consulted during our scientific research.

First of all, we should note that the existence of information given in some secondary sources that the translation of the Holy Qur'an into English began in the middle of the 17th century does not lead to the conclusion that the English were unaware of the Holy Qur'an until that time. The reason is that most sources in this regard show that the British people were familiar with the Holy Qur'an from the 12th century.

In particular, according to the famous Indian linguist, Abdur Raheem Kidwai (2007), he wrote that English-speaking peoples first became acquainted with the Holy Qur'an in the middle of the twelfth century through Quran translations in Latin.² It can be seen that another linguist, Charles Brunett, in his scientific research on this topic, made similar conclusions to Abdur Raheem Kidwai's comments. As just one example, Brunett noted in one of his articles (2004) that the priest Robert Catton, who translated the Holy Qur'an into Latin in 1143 under the name "Lex Mahomet pseudoprophete", was also originally from England.³ This is according to the information obtained from the National Archives of England,⁴ This priest, who was the special correspondent of the British kingdom in Spain, was also considered a member of the Toledo School of Translation in Spain at the same time.⁵

Based on the above considerations, taking into account that most of the English translations of the Holy Qur'an are not translated directly from the Arabic

² Abdur Raheem Kidwai. (2007) *Bibliography of the Translations of the Meanings of the Glorious Quran into English: 1641—2002: A Critical Study*. Al Madinah Al Munavvarah: King Fahd Quran printing complex, 474 pages.

³ Charles Burnett, "Ketton, Robert of (fl. 1141–1157)", *Oxford Dictionary of National Biography* (Oxford University Press, 2004).

⁴ The National Archives Annual Report (XII–XIV centuries) (PDF), The National Archives, 15 July 2010, archived (PDF) from the original on 17 December 2010, retrieved 19 December 2010.

⁵ Dunlop, D. M. (1960). The work of Translation at Toledo. *Babel*, 6(2), 55-59.

language, but rather from proselytizing translations in French and Latin, we did a research over the history of the Quran translations in English and as a result of our studies, we witnessed the existence of the following translations, which are quite different from each other in terms of ideological diversity:

I. NON – MUSLIM TRANSLATIONS

1. Aleksandr Ross (1649) *Alcoran of Mahomet*. London.: Anno Dom press, 454 pages.
2. George Sale (1734) *Alcoran of Mohammed*. London: C. Ackers press, 564 pages.
3. John Medows Rodwell (1861) *The Koran*. London: J. M. Dent & Sons Ltd. 612 pages.
4. Edward Henry Palmer (1880) *The Quran*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 856 pages.
5. Richard Bell (1939) “The Qur'an”. Edinburgh: T. & T. Clark, 430 pages.
6. Arthur Arberry (1955) “The Koran Interpreted”. New York: Macmillan, 601 pages.
7. N.J. Dawood (1956) *The Koran: A New Translation*. New York: Penguin readers press, 340 pages.
8. Thomas Clearly (2004) *The Qur'an: A New Translation*. United States.: Starlatch Press, 510 pages.
9. Alan Jones (2007) “The Qur'an”. Edinburgh.: Edinburgh University Press. 528 pages.
10. A.J Droge. Sheffield. (2012) *The Qur'an: A New Annotated Translation*. Equinox Publishing Limited. 700 pages.
11. Jane Dammen McAuliffe. (2017) *The Qur'an (Norton Critical Editions)*. New York: W. W. Norton & Company, 578 pages.
12. Gordon D. Nickel. (2020) *The Quran with Christian Commentary*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan Academic press, 611 pages.

13. Robert B. Spencer. (2022) *The Critical Qur'an: Explained from Key Islamic Commentaries and Contemporary Historical Research*. New York: Bombardier Books, 401 pages

II. SUNNI TRANSLATIONS:

14. Hairat Dihlawi. (1916) *The Koran*. Delhi: M. H. Press, 412 pages.
15. Muhammad Marmaduke Pickthall. (1930) *The Meaning of the Glorious Koran*. New York: A. A. Knopf press, 534 pages.
16. Abdullah Yusuf Ali. (1934) *The Holy Qur'an: Translation and Commentary*. Lahore: Shaik Muhammad Ashraf Publishers of Bakhshi Bazaar, 476 pages.
17. Abdul Majid Daryabadi (1957) *Tafseru-l-Qur'aan* India.: Darul Ishaat press, 1265 pages.
18. Khadim Rahmani Nuri of Shillong, (1964) *The Running Commentary of the Holy Quran* India.: Sufi Hamsaya-Gurudwar press. 671 pages.
19. Muhammad Akbar. (1967) *The Meaning of the Qur'an*. Lahore: Pendikan press, 678 pages
20. Hashim Amir Ali (1974) *The Message of the Qur'an*. Rutland: C. E. Tuttle Co., 718 pages.
21. Muhammad Asad. (1980) *The Message of the Qur'an*. Gibraltar: Dar al-Andalus Limited press, 602 pages.
22. Thomas Ballantyne Irving (1985) *The Qur'an: The First American Version*. Brattleboro.: Amana Books press, 589 pages.
23. Ahmed Ali (1988) *Al-Qur'an: A Contemporary Translation*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 432 pages.
24. Muhammad Khalilur Rahman (1991) *The Clarion Call of the Eternal Quran*. Dhaka.: Pengkalan press, 610 pages.
25. Ahmad Zidan and Mrs. Dina Zidan (1993) *The Glorious Qur'an*. Islamic Inc. Publishing house, 411 pages.

26. Mir Aneesuddin (1993) *A Simple Translation of the Holy Quran*. Hyderabad.: Islamic Academy of Sciences, 510 pages.
27. Syed Vickar Ahamed (1999) *The Glorious Qur'an*. Kuala Lumpur: TR Group of Companies, 853 pages.
28. Emily B. Assami (1997) *The Holy Qur'an*. Jeddah: Dar Abul Qasim Publishing House, 700 pages.
29. M. Farooq-e-Azam Malik (1997) *Al-Qur'an: Guidance for Mankind*. Dearborn: The Institute of Islamic Knowledge, 670 pages.
30. Muhammad Mahmoud Ghali. *Towards Understanding the Ever-glorious Qur'an*. Cairo: Publishing House for Universities, 390 pages.
31. Abdalhaqq Bewley and Aisha Bewley (1999) *The Noble Qur'an: A New Rendering of Its Meaning in English*. London: Madinah Press, 518 pages.
32. Muhammad Muhsin Khan and Muhammad Taqi-ud-Din al-Hilali (1999) *Interpretation of the Meanings of the Noble Qur'an*. Chicago: Kazi Publications Inc. 433 pages.
33. Nureddin Uzunoğlu (2000) *The Majestic Qur'an: An English Rendition of Its Meanings*. United States: Starlatch Press. 678 pages.
34. Majid Fakhry (2002) *An Interpretation of the Qur'an*. New York: NYU Press, 419 pages.
35. Zohurul Hoque (2000) *Translation and Commentary on The Holy Quran*. Holy Quran Publishing Project, 601 pages.
36. M. J. Gohari (2002) *The Qur'an*. Oxford: Oxford Logos Society, 560 pages.
37. Shaikh Basheer Ahmed Muhuyiddin. *Quran: The Living Truth*. Kerala: Manas Foundation, 809 pages.
38. Nooruddeen Durkee (2003) *The Tajwidi Qur'an*. Charlottesville: An-noor Educational Foundation. 562 pages.
39. M.A.S. Abdel-Haleem (2004) *The Qur'an* (Oxford World Classics). Oxford: Oxford University Press, 739 pages.

40. Muhammad Karam Shah Al-Azhari and Anis Ahmad Sheikh. (2004) *Jamal Ul Qur'an (The Beauteous Qur'an)*. 3rd edition. Translated by Lahore-Karachi: Zia-ul-Qur'an Publications, 2004.
41. Afzal Hoosen Elias (2007) *Quran Made Easy*. Karachi: Zam Zam Publishers, 527 pages.
42. Muhammad Taqi Usmani. (2007) *The Meanings of the Noble Qur'an with Explanatory Notes*. 2 volumes. Idarat al-Maarif, 789 pages.
43. Ali Ünal (2008) *The Qur'an with Annotated Interpretation in Modern English*. Clifton: Tughra Books, 815 pages.
44. Ahmad Zaki Hammad. (2008) *The Gracious Qur'an: A Modern Phrased Interpretation in English*. Reston: Lucent Interpretations, 493 pages.
45. Tarif Khalidi. *The Qur'an: (2009) A New Translation*. New York: Penguin Classics, 431 pages.
46. Muhammad Tahir-ul-Qadri. (2009) *Irfan ul Quran*. London: Minhaj-ul-Quran Publications, 369 pages.
47. Yahiya Emerick. (2010) *The Holy Qur'an: Guidance for Life*. Islamic Foundation of North America/Amirah Publishing Co., 520 pages.
48. Imtiaz Ahmad. (2010) *The Easy Qur'an*. Farmington Hills: Tawheed Center of Farmington Hills, 603 pages.
49. Maulana Wahiduddin Khan. (2011) *The Quran: Translation and Commentary with Parallel Arabic Text*. India, Goodword, 817 pages.
50. Muhammad Tahir-ul-Qadri. (2011) *The Glorious Qur'an*. London: Minhaj-ul-Quran Publications, 782 pages.
51. Assad Nimer Busool. (2012) *The Wise Qur'an: A Modern English Translation*. Washington. CoPress 410 pages.
52. Talal Itani (2012) *Quran in English: Clear and Easy to Read*. Clear Quran foundation press, 368 pages.

53. Abdur Raheem Kidwai. (2013) *What is in the Quran? Message of the Quran in Simple English*. New Delhi: Viva Books, 635 pages.
54. Fode Drame. (2014) *Anwar-ul-Quran: The Holy Quran with English Translation*. Scotts Valley: CreateSpace Independent Publishing, 718 pages.
55. Mustafa Khattab. (2018) *The Clear Quran: A Thematic English Translation*. St. Catharines: SirajPublications, 488 pages.
56. Sayed Jumaa Salam. (2018) *Noor Al Bayan. English*. Sacramento: Salam Educational Center, 503 pages.
57. Musharraf Hussain al Azhari. (2018) *The Majestic Quran: A Plain English Translation*. Nottingham: Invitation Publishing, 486 pages.
58. Adil Salahi. (2019) *The Qur'an: A Translation for the 21st Century*. Villa Park: The Islamic Foundation, 775 pages.
59. Shehzad Saleem. (2022) *The Qur'an Translated*. Al-Mawrid press, 401 pages.
60. Nuh Ha Mim Keller. (2022) *The Quran Beheld: An English Translation from the Arabic*. Beltsville: Amana Publications, 590 pages.

III. SHIA TRANSLATIONS

61. Mirza Abul Fazl. (1911) *The Qur'an*. Allahabad: Asgar & Co. 911 pages.
62. Mohammed Habib Shakir *The Qur'an*. New York: Tahirke Tarsile Qur'an, 680 pages.
63. Muhammad Sarwar. (1981) *The Holy Qur'an: The Arabic Text and English Translation* Englewood: The Islamic Seminary Inc., 810 pages.
64. Syed V. Mir Ahmed Ali. (1999) *The Holy Qur'an*. Tehran: Osweh Printing & Publication Co., 403 pages.
65. Fazlollah Nikayin. (2000) *The Quran: A Poetic Translation*. Theology press. 711 pages.
66. Tahere Saffarzadeh. (2001) *The Qur'an in Persian and English*. TehranME press 781 pages.

67. Ali Quli Qara'i. (2005) *The Qur'an with an English Paraphrase*, Iranian Centre for Translation of the Holy Qur'an/Islamic Publications International, 406 pages.
68. Laleh Bakhtiar. (2007) *The Sublime Qur'an*. Chicago: Kazi Publications, Inc., 567 pages.
69. Ali Salami. (2009) *The Magnificent Qur'an: A 21st Century English Translation*. Tempe: Leilah Publication, 386 pages.

IV. AHMADIY TRANSLATIONS

70. Mohammad Khan. (1905) *The Holy Qur'an*. Patiala: Rajinder Press, 501 pages.
71. Maulana Muhammad Ali. (1917) *The English Translation of the Holy Qur'an with Commentary*. (1917) Punjab, 412 pages.
72. Maulvi Sher Ali. (1955) *The Holy Quran: Arabic Text and English Translation*. Netherlands press. 723 pages.
73. Maulvi Sher Ali, Mirza Bashir Ahmad and Malik Ghulam Farid. (1963) *The English Commentary of the Holy Quran*. 5 volumes. Muslim Community press, 630 pages.
74. Pir Salahuddin. (1969) *The Wonderful Koran: A New English Translation*. Eminabad: The Raftar-I-Zamana Publications, 690 pages.
75. Muhammad Zafrulla Khan. (1970) *The Quran*. London: Curzon Press, 561 pages.
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V. TRANSLATIONS BY PROPHETIC SUNNAH DENIERS

77. Rashad Khalifa. (1981) *Quran: The Final Testament*. Islamic Productions, 489 pages.
78. Ghulam Ahmed Pervez. (1996) *Exposition of the Holy Quran*. Lahore: Tolu-E-Islam Trust, 671 pages.

79. Shabbir Ahmed. (2003) *The Qur'an as It Explains Itself*. Bedford: Lighthouse, 747 pages.
80. Edip Yuksel, Layth Saleh al-Shaiban, and Martha Schulte-Nafeh. (2007) *The Quran: A Reformist Translation*. London: Brainbow Press, 796 pages.
81. Monotheistic Group. (2008) *The Message - A Translation of the Glorious Qur'an*. London: Brainbow Press, 671 pages.
82. Seyyed Hossein Nasr, Caner K. Dagli, Maria Massi Dakake, Joseph E. B. Lumbard, and Mohammed Rustom. (2015) *The Study Quran: A New Translation and Commentary* New York: HarperOne, 586 pages.

As you can see, above are attached the spiritual translations of the Holy Qur'an in English based on the ideas of different ideological views and orientations. For this reason, it can be concluded that in any linguistic translation of the Quran into English under the name "Quran" or "Koran" will have an impact of ideological views that are characterized among particular religious communities.

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